

1 **A systems biologic description of transcriptional activity associated with Xist activation resulting**
2 **from DNA damage illuminated by H2AX mutation.**

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7 53bp1 and BRCA1 control autosomal activation of Xist, suggesting H2AX decoration of active damage
8 sites is also associated with Xist modulation resulting from damage or repair of the DNA. We studied total
9 transcription in cells containing a mutation in H2AFX which results in loss of H2AX expression and
10 observed strong control of Xist by H2AX. Loss of H2AX expression resulted in activation of Xist, and was
11 accompanied by failure to activate ATM and a paradoxical activation of ATRX. Loss of H2AX function
12 resulting in Xist activation occurred together with activation of Rad52 and Rad18 but silencing of Rad23b.
13 While BRCA1 activation was completely lost, MRE11A was impaired but not silenced. Mechanistically, we
14 demonstrate a functional link between non-coding, imprinting-based control of the X-inactivation center
15 (XIC) through activation of the topologically associated ncRNA FIRRE resulting from H2AX mutation
16 concomitant with Xist activation that occurs as a direct consequence of modulation of DNA damage
17 signaling resulting from H2AX mutation. Thus, DNA damage signal strength controls Xist activation and
18 repression at the XIC and proceeds through FIRRE activation.
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